

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Report on Cycle 2 hackathon
Deliverable number	D24 (Del. Rel. No. D4.4)
Revision	0
Status	Final
Planned delivery date	28/02/2023
Actual date of issue	28/02/2023
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	MISU
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

This document is a report on the Cycle 2 hackathon, in which stakeholders will be invited to contribute to the implementation of online diagnostics for solar and wind power production in the SR-ESMs.

Work package in charge:

WP4

Lead author:

Frida Bender

Other contributing authors:

Thorsten Mauritsen

Internal reviewer(s):

1st reviewer: Elina Plesca

2nd reviewer: Heike Konow

Contacts: frida.bender@misu.su.se

Visit us on: www.nextgems-h2020.eu

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1 Executive summary

The second NextGEMS Hackathon was lead by the Storms & Radiation theme. Project members from all themes gathered for a week in Vienna, to analyse the cycle 2 simulations with the NextGEMS models. Stipend holding students worked on implementation of online diagnostics for wind power prouction in the SR-ESMs, advised by invited stakeholders from the renewable energy sector.

2 Conclusion & Results

The second NextGEMS hackathon, was successfully held in Vienna. Following a dedicated data handling workshop, different aspects of the Cycle 2 simulations were analysed by each of the themes Storms & Land, Storms & Ocean, and Storms & Radiation. Challenge problems of simulated wind energy potential were addressed, with some involvement from stake holders from the renewable energy sector. Communication was ensured by recording of science explaining videos, by Storms & Society.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes
O2	

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no
O3	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP4**Relevance in this deliverable?**

To stabilize the climate of next-generation models by balancing top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiation and implement a simplified aerosol scheme, in order to enable studies of Earth's climate sensitivity and aerosol forcing in the Application phase (WP5). (O1)

yes

To identify shortcomings related to remaining sub-grid scale processes, including representation of turbulent transport and mixing, cloud microphysics and subgrid cloud structures. (O1)

no

To implement online diagnostics of wind energy potential in an innovative bi-directional endeavour, jointly with stakeholders, in order to prepare an assessment of the impacts of changing emissions of CO₂ and aerosols on efforts to replace fossil fuels with renewable energy in the Application phase. (O3)

yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

Hackathons are communal exploration, analysis and development activities – all various forms of ‘hacking’. They prioritize working together over lecturing. At nextGEMS meetings, our fingers do the talking. The aim of this report is the description of the second of such project meetings, the Cycle 2 Hackathon. It took place from 28th of June to 02nd of July 2022. In total, 92 people, including 15 stipend holders and two stakeholders out of the renewable energy sector, from 35 institutions across Europe travelled to Vienna to meet in-person for four days of intense coding and discussions (see Fig. 1 for a group photo).

Some statistics are summarized in section 4.3.

In the following, we illustrate the different aspects of the hackathon through photos and in a video that gives a feeling for the atmosphere on site. Photos with impressions of the activities are found in Fig. 2.

This hackathon was co-funded by EASiWACE2, another project funded through the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. - 823988.

The hackathon was held in Vienna, Austria, at two different locations; pre-hackathon data handling workshop, as well as closing discussions were held at the Univerisy of Vienna, while the bulk of the hackathon took place at the co-working space Talent Garden.

4.1 Hackathon components

See also photo (Figure 2) and video [video](#) documentation.

1. Introduction of models, model output and data access (training component)

A pre-hackathon data handling workshop was offered on Tuesday June 28. This included presentations of the ICON and IFS models; their physics, component coupling, resolution, output structure etc, as well as presentations and hands-on practice on accessing and working with NextGEMS data, and sharing code. The session was streamed and recorded, and presentation material made available.

2. Opening discussion, introduction of the four themes as well as challenge problems

The hackathon was opened properly on Wednesday June 29, with a welcome speech by local host Aiko Voigt (U Wien). The latest developments in each of the NextGEMS models was presented by MPI and ECMWF. Each of the themes presented their respective planned activities for the hackathon. In addition, the Challenge Problems related to renewable energy, was introduced. Bjorn Stevens’ overview talk of NextGEMS progress wrapped up the introductory session, which was also streamed for remote participants.

3. Group work / hacking

The group work was organised so that each theme had a number of subgroups, that were formed around the defined focus questions of each theme. Storms & Land worked on creating an overview of the surface energy balance in the storm resolving models, and extracting radiation statistics for the Cabauw surroundings. Storms & Ocean worked

on air-sea interaction, and on tropical circulation and mixed layer heat budget. Storms & Radiation worked on analysis of, and remedies for energy leaks in the models, as well as aerosol implementation and cloud evaluation. In addition, the 15 early career stipend holders made an additional group, working on renewable energy, in particular solar and wind energy. Storms & Society focused on renewable energy story lines, and organised a workshop on this theme. They also organised the Science Explainers recordings.

4. Networking component: not only during group work, but also in breaks and extra-curricular activities.

In this second hackathon, the networking component continued for both experienced and new members of the NextGEMS community. On the first pre-hackathon evening, a welcoming barbeque for Early Career Scientists was arranged, and the whole meeting ended with an afternoon hike, followed by dinner on Saturday evening.

During the hackathon, lunches, coffee breaks, as well as on-site evening events gave ample opportunity for social interaction.

On Wednesday, Lena Vogelmann (University of Vienna) gave a talk, followed by an open and much appreciated discussion on Unconscious Bias in Science. On Friday after dinner our guest Prof. Masaki Satoh (University of Tokyo) presented his valued perspective on the History and Future of km-scale Climate Modelling, this too was followed by an open discussion

As in the previous hackathon, everyone took part in the Social Network Analysis survey, arranged by Storms & Science.

5. Science communication: recordings of science explainers

Science explainers for the NextGEMS website were produced, and can be found on [nextGEMS website](#). In these short videos, NextGEMS scientists present underlying science, and progress made in the project, in plain language. The explainers aim to show how scientists think and their way of working and cover a wide range of topics relevant to any audience interested in the latest breakthroughs related to storm-resolving Earth Systems Models (SR-ESMs).

6. Closing discussion with results and collecting tasks for the model development towards Cycle 2 runs

Each of the research themes presented some of their most fascinating results, and issues that they encountered. This included for instance evaluation of the models in terms of mixed-layer heat budget, cold-tongue development, and frequency and intensity of tropical cyclones (Storms & Ocean), energy balance, water balance, and circulation (Storms & Land), clouds and radiation, mesoscale organization of convection, and cloud-aerosol coupling (Storms & Radiation). Storms & Society summarised the story telling workshop and encouraged continued participation in networking surveys and vlogging. The challenge problem group presented examples of model processing that could support solar and wind energy production planning. The summarising presentations were followed by a feedback and discussion round including the planning of Cycle 3. The closing discussions were streamed, for remote participants.

Figure 1: Group photo of all participants. Photo by T. Vostry, Latest Thinking.

4.2 Knowledge co-production: challenge problems on renewable energy

The stipend holders in the challenge problem team were advised by stakeholders from the renewable energy sector; consultants from Iberdrola and Vestas participated and/or provided input, that helped them understand the problems that the renewable energy sector is facing. These sessions also provided the opportunity to discuss results with experts, and learn about potential careers in the renewable energy sector. The teams also got technical support from members of the modelling groups, so that they could focus on the science rather than solving technical problems.

The teams were provided with wind speed, as well as direct and diffuse solar radiation data from ICON and IFS, and were challenged to combine these data, and/or other model output, to support the design of renewable energy systems. The approach taken in the hackathon is to use the ability of the NextGEMS models to resolve the mesoscales and represent relevant motion and fields for renewable energy production. We used primarily dedicated high frequency output for a series of stations, but also the complete mapped output.

It became clear during the hackathon that the wind industry is already working with quite advanced modelling tools for site planning and short term forecasting of wind power, along with on-site observations. The situation is slightly less advanced for solar power, partly because the modelling tools are not nearly of the same quality due to problems with modelling clouds. New demands on the industry to also assess the impact of the changing climate on production, safety and durability/maintenance needs is a challenge that the industry is not yet well suited to meet, and where more research is urgently needed.

It is also clear that industry is looking forward to leveraging NextGEMS-like simulations in their workflow.

Figure 2: Photo documentation of the Cycle 2 Hackathon in Vienna, Austria. Main components visible in the photos are the group work, e.g. people hacking together in groups on similar topics, plenary discussion, workshop activities and video shooting. On top, we recorded several Science Explainer videos as part of our communication strategy followed by WP10. Photos by Yuting Wu, MPI-M.

4.3 Statistics

We include basic statistics to monitor the gender and training potential of the Hackathons in Figure 3.

In meetings, especially the hackathons, we keep an eye on equal representation of all genders. Whenever there is a choice based on the scientific background, we give preference to traditionally under-represented genders as well as early career scientists for holding presentations or leading a working group.

4.4 Data handling

In preparation to the hackathon, the first day was dedicated to an intensive data-handling workshop, where newcomers and advanced nextGEMS members were updated on the model runs from IFS and ICON and data processing activities. Updated scripts are collected in the online book [easy.gems](https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/) and shall make people familiar with the simulation output and facilitate the efficient analysis of such large datasets. The online book is a growing and collaborative effort available at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/> and is further described in the deliverable D2.1.

Figure 3: Gender, age, and career stage statistics for participants of the nextGEMS Cycle 2 Hackathon. Source: Survey via LimeSurvey, where 50% of the participants filled-in the survey.

5 References (Bibliography)

Not applicable.

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The detailed description of this hackathon could benefit organizers of similar events. The format in which new project participants work together has proven to be successful in building a consortium. This document will be freely available to the general public from the project website and linked to subsequent Hackathon advertisements to motivate young scientists and people from stakeholder groups to engage with the project.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable contributes to O1 under A1, by organisation of the hackathon and evaluation of the latest model versions' simulations, and A3 by testing implementation of climatological aerosol plumes, coupled to radiation and cloud schemes. O3 under A4 and A5, by further competence and community building not only among young and more experienced scientists in the project, but also with external partners and stake holders within the renewable energy sector.

The report on the Cycle 2 hackathon applies to the WP4 specific objectives of ensuring a stable radiation balance, and is specifically linked to the WP4 deliverable D4.1 describing in detail the work with balancing the TOA fluxes in the NextGEMS models. It also applies to the WP4 specific objective to implement online diagnostics of wind energy potential into NextGEMS models, and links to the [report on NextGEMS challenge problems](#) (Milestone 8). It also relates to WP2 deliverable D2.3 describing the data workflow, and includes some aspects of the gender and training strategy described in D1.2.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Website <https://nextgems-h2020.eu> online
- Cycle 1 Hackathon, 19.10. - 22.10.2021 in Berlin

- "Science meets Art" - Activity: NextCalendArt 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 1.-3.4.2022 near Madrid
- weekly Office Hours for internal communication and dissemination on topics such as (i) current state of IFS and ICON developments, (ii) Knowledge Coproduction with the solar energy industry, (iii) data handling with *intake*, and many more.
- Cycle 2 Hackathon, 28.06. - 02.07.2022 in Vienna

11 Full track of publications and IP

No publications so far.